

Manual Book on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

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1. Introduction

This manual serves as a guide for GeneBEcon project communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities from 2023 to 2025. Its purpose is to help consortium partners meet their communication obligations. **All consortium partners are bound by the Grant Agreement to provide input to the WP on communication, dissemination and exploitation for communication purposes and also to take part in dissemination themselves:** “The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.”

The manual outlines strategies for effectively launching and sharing project information with the broader public through various channels, including social media and events. This document is derived from Deliverable D4.1, titled the Initial Communication and Engagement Plan, and is informed by the insights gained from the communication plan co-created during the Systems Mapping workshop on March 1st, 2023.

This document forms a part of the contractual agreement between all involved parties associated with GeneBEcon and Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI).

2. Types of Events

This chapter provides a non-exhaustive list of events that can be organised to present your results, parts of your results or other specific parts of the project. WP on communication, dissemination and exploitation will support you by communicating about the event as well as helping you with event-related communication items. Please consult the Event Checklist at the bottom of this document for a step-by-step guide on what you should not miss in your planning. The events can be of any size and format. Here we provide you with a few examples:

- Science on the Streets: a gathering in public spaces, engaging with citizens
- SoapboxScience: an initiative hosting annual events worldwide, specifically for women scientists
- Pint of Science: annual events where science is shared in an informal setting like bars
- Science Slam: poetry events
- Open Doors Day
- Fairs, exhibitions, forums
- Workshops: within or outside your institution
- Talks: presentations at universities, schools and other relevant educational institutions

3. Organising an Event

This section provides guidelines on communication surrounding organising an event. Regardless of the event's scale or nature, it's crucial to follow these guidelines whenever you are introducing GeneBEcon in any capacity.

3.1 Pre-Event

Based on the Grant Agreement, all partners are obligated to give at **least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries together with sufficient information on the results intended for dissemination**. Any other beneficiary may object within 15 days of receiving notification. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

The following items must be considered before the event.

- Title of the Event
- Description of the Event:
 - Brief background
 - Objective
 - Date, time and location
 - Speakers
 - Target audience
- Communications Tools, depending on the format of the event:
 - Brochure
 - Roll-Up
 - Flyer

- Poster
 - Camera
 - Tripod
- Additional material required from WP on communication, dissemination and exploitation: for example if a press release is needed, make sure to note that in the Section

Based on that, the communication team will launch a social media including:

- Event Timeline
- Minimum 1 content piece for **Linked-In** and **Twitter** with
 - “Count Down” Content
 - Graphic material related to the topic of the event
 - Copywriting about the upcoming event

3.2 During the Event

Since the effectiveness of communication depends on contributions from events across various countries, it is essential that partners share photographs or videos from all events they attend that relate to GeneBEcon.

For the event to be disseminated on the same day, please submit the material on this link on the day of the event.

The following items must be considered during the event.

- Take photos/videos during the event with your cell phone
- If a professional photographer is present, ask him to forward you the photos
- If possible, record a short video of stakeholders at the event, asking simple questions concerning the project (Example: What comes to mind when you hear new genomic techniques? What potential do you think GeneBEcon has for the future of our food system?)

Based on that, the communication team will prepare:

- Minimum 1 content piece for **Linked-In** and **Twitter** with
 - Photo and/or video material
 - Copywriting

3.3 Post-Event

After the event, the organisers should submit a brief report: agenda, number of participants, topics covered, and main outcomes and send it to the link above.

Based on this and the previous submissions, the communication team will prepare:

- Minimum 1 content for **Linked-In** and **Twitter** with:
 - Picture or Video
 - Copywriting
 - Audience Interaction Content, if relevant

The communication team will share a summary report of the event on GeneBEcon website, under News and Events. If a press release is needed, communication team will write on based on the provided information.

3.4 Examples

Agenda 2023	April														March															
	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Pre-event																														
Submitting the form																														
Creating Timeline																														
Preparing Campaign																														
Finalisation of the Communication																														
Posting the "Count Down"																														
Posting other content																														
Event																														
The Event																														
Receiving communication material																														
Posting the content																														
Post-Event																														
Receiving communication material																														
Preparing communication material																														
Posting the content																														

Figure 1: Timeline example

Figure 2: Twitter and LinkedIn Content

4. Attending an Event

Partners are encouraged to participate in external events to showcase the work conducted as part of the GeneBEcon project. This involvement could encompass a wide range of activities, such as delivering presentations at universities, giving talks, hosting workshops, or participating in fairs, among others. The scale of the event is not a critical factor; any form of dissemination or project discussion is valuable. **Since** GeneBEcon's communication efforts are thoroughly evaluated **and we must provide metrics and quantitatively significant results**, it is essential to report all these activities. Additionally, please take this opportunity to record any past activities that have not yet been shared in the provided form.

When you attend an event, please make sure that you are using GeneBEcon communication materials – when you fill out the form noted above, the communication team will be notified and will forward the required materials.

5. Annex 1: Event Checklist

Internal Document:

Event Checklist

This document is a short informal help sheet - for more information regarding project events refer to the Manual Book on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation.

It includes:

- 1) a non-exhaustive checklist to help you out with the planning of any events during the GeneBEcon project (p. 2-6)
- 2) a wording cheat sheet + objectives (p. 7-8)

We compiled items that are often missed but are crucial to keep up professionalism and help the events run smoothly.

There is space at the end of the checklist to add your own points.

Please make sure you tick off the items: either print out the checklist or tick it off in a PDF version.

Event Organisation

3 months before the event

- Fill out the communication and dissemination reporting form (deadline: 15 days prior to the event)
- Secure the venue
- Identify and invite relevant participants
Tips: Emails should ideally be tailored to each participant, demonstrating why it is vital that they attend and how this event is relevant for them. If it is not possible to tailor for each participant, at least tailor to each profile type.
- Send out a "save the date" as soon as you agree on it, preferably with a **calendar** event reminder
- Send out a Calendar invite and confirmation to registered people

Sign-up form should include:

- Date, title, venue, organisers
- Collect dietary restrictions if relevant
- Ask for organisation type, position, stakeholder group (academia, industry, farmers, decision-and-policymakers, civil society organizations, consumers, other)
- Ask for consent to send updates on the project →
Once registration is closed: add those who agree to the stakeholder file.
- GDPR disclaimer
*(Template:
By registering for this event, I agree that my personal data is used for administration purposes related to the event.
By registering for this event, I consent to photos and recordings taken of me during the event. The material may be used by the organizers for communication and dissemination purposes such as online content, in information material, news releases etc. Your decision to give your consent is voluntary and can be withdrawn at any time, for which please contact the organizers and/or photographer on-site.)*

- *if possible, offer hybrid and in-person participation*

In the monthly WP meeting: communicate the plan + clearly state and divide all responsibilities

Get consent from all partners for the content you are sharing! (*Intellectual Property Sensitive Approach, a minimum of 15 days in advance, as per the Grant Agreement*)

Agenda related:

Plan breaks and time for informal interactions ("networking")

Plan refreshments and, if relevant, lunch

Assign a moderator

If recruiting other partners to help design an event, be sure to ask in advance and include them in the planning.

Use **this link** to feature our social media in any promo materials, find the QR code for this link below:

linktr.ee/genebecon

2 months before the event

- Check who has registered and make sure that you have balanced stakeholder representation. If not: get underrepresented profiles to attend (ask partners for help if needed)
- Send Pre-work, if relevant: surveys, feedback on the topic, etc. Make sure it requires a maximum of 30 minutes of their time and clearly communicate the deadline

1 month before the event

- Send out a reminder + agenda

2 days before

- Send out a reminder + arrival information (if in person)
- Prepare name tags

At the event:

- Have clear sign/poster/roll up for building and/or room
- Assign a timekeeper

- Assign at least one person to take short videos (e.g. a short prompt answered by a few attendants) / photos and submit the Information to the WP on communication, dissemination and exploitation.

 Also to do if you attend any external events!

Photos Guidelines

- Capture images that incorporate branding elements, (logos, banners)
- Take pictures where people engage in discussion
- Take pictures of the crowd (during break networking, seated crowd)
- Take pictures of presenters, preferably with their presentation visible
- Document a range of activities (presentations, discussions, networking, and any hands-on activities)
- Schedule time for group photos of participants, speakers, and organizers
- Take simple stock photos, even if just with your phone for example:

After the event:

- Fill out the communication and dissemination reporting form
- Send out a thank you email to all who attended
- Send out a feedback survey
- Send out a recording/presentations/other material to the participants

